

FORMING FLEXIBLE SKILLS OF STUDENTS**Shadek Nurtilek***Master student of Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages,
Kazakhstan, Almaty*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928259>**Abstract**

In the article, the issues of the development of soft skills among students of senior classes are considered. Soft skills are universal personality skills. The concept of "soft skills" can be described in terms of general trends in personality development. There are certain development conditions for this. Conditions for the formation of soft skills are a happy family situation, the organization of the educational process, digital competence, and the development of communication skills. Soft skills are one of the criteria for the effectiveness of academic and professional activity of a person. The presence of developed skills largely determines the success of a person. The use of this information in the process of learning at school can have a positive impact on the development of the student's personality. The conclusion about the special conditions for the development of soft skills in children of senior school age.

Keywords: *soft skills, universal skills, high school students, school, competences, creativity, communication*

Currently, prestigious organizations such as the Center for Curriculum Design, the World Economic Forum, and the Organization for Economic Development and Cooperation identify the influence of several global trends that significantly affect changes in society based on independent research. Among them, the most important and common trends are: firstly, the rapid pace of changes in living conditions and world conditions. Secondly, the constant and continuous development of technologies and society determines the change of the professional field to a significant extent. Accordingly, these trends set requirements for the quality of people necessary for effective service in the context of ongoing changes, which is primarily characterized by soft skills.

The increase in the need for social or flexible skills can be explained primarily by today's increasing penetration of the economy and labor markets, and the increasing demand for competent employees with social and intercultural skills. As the world's economies become more interconnected, multiple language and intercultural skills are becoming increasingly important on a global scale. That is why the development of these skills is not only a trend in modern education, but also demands the elaboration of its structural content.

"Flexible skills" is a relatively new term (these skills are also called soft or transitive skills). Unlike

"hard skills", which are directly related to the qualifications and professional competences of the graduate, soft skills are universal, non-specialized and often related to personal qualities and social skills. Today, flexible skills are aimed at responding to the successful professional and scientific, life adaptation of graduates of higher education institutions and young scientists.

Today, due to global trends, the professional field is also undergoing qualitative changes. Employers are demanding from professionals well-developed flexible skills (soft skills) that help them to adapt to rapidly changing conditions and effectively implement professional activities. T.A. Yarkova, I. I. Cherkasova emphasizes that these skills are an important educational result, therefore she concludes that it is necessary to organize their targeted development within the educational process. According to D. Tataurschikova, as the specialist moves up the career ladder, he begins to use soft skills in his work in large quantities, and professional skills - hard skills - are not as important as before.

The vast majority of foreign scientists define flexible skills as a group of personal qualities, skills, emotional intelligence, personality attributes, etc. widely considered as a set. Among them, skills are defined as universal skills important for professional activity, and we can see their full content in the following table (table 1).

Table 1

Content of description given to soft skills:

№	Authors	Reference Contents
1	L. K. Raitskaya, E. V. Tikhonova	Soft skills - a set of non-professional skills, personal qualities and attributes that are in demand in the labor market for the effective implementation of professional competence
2	L. K. Salnaya	Soft skills - use other components of the individual: "a combination of certain personal qualities, emotional intelligence, communicative competence that allow a specialist to achieve professional success. It has the priority to help a person effectively solve the situations that arise at the workplace and to expand the area of his employment.
3	L. H. Lippman, R. Ryberg, R. Carney, A. Christine	Soft skills are a set of several other, multi-dimensional components of an individual, that is, skills, competence, behavior, facilities, personal qualities that allow people to navigate effectively in their environment, work with others, perform their work effectively, as well as achieve their goals. wide set
4	E. Dall'Amico, S. Verona	Soft skills are non-specific and closely related to personal qualities and dispositions (confidence, discipline, self-management), social (communication, teamwork, emotional intelligence) and management abilities (time management, problem solving, critical thinking).
5	V. Shipilov	soft skills are socio-psychological skills that can be useful and necessary for a person in many life situations
6	A. Yarkova, .I. Cherkasova	Soft skills are described as follows: these are universal skills that are important and necessary for successful professional and life self-determination of people, regardless of professional field or profession.

Based on the considered definitions, the following characteristics of soft skills can be divided:

- Soft skills are not just skills, but a wide set of qualities (personal qualities, intellectual features, facilities, skills, etc.) related to the implementation and development in life and professional activities.

- Soft skills are understood as personal qualities, universal skills, non-professional and acquired skills that affect the efficiency of human activity.

- They are not related to the specifics of professional activity, i.e. soft skills are common to various types of professional activity.

M. E. Volkova says that they are not only necessary in real life situations, but also important for the activity of any specialist, dividing "soft skills of communication, leadership, teamwork, need, public speaking, "thinking" and others" [1]. He says that acquiring only professional skills does not help a specialist to fully realize himself, and that well-developed soft skills are necessary.

Foreign scientists L. H. Lippman, R. Ryberg, etc. b. when defining the concept of "soft skills" in their work, they pay attention to their goals and importance - why and why a person needs them, first of all, because they enable success in work and life; secondly, it is explained by the fact that it is used in solving a wide range of tasks related to professional self-identification, development, and problem solving, as well as being highly valued by employers.

If we compare social skills with traditional practice, it is first of all combined with functionally im-

portant qualities. Because operationally important qualities are "the quality of an individual that affects the effectiveness of the types of activities and forms of activities performed by a professional and is manifested through them". From the point of view of duty, the specialist solves two groups of tasks: professional and individual tasks of professional formation and implementation. Accordingly, a person can perform two types of activity - professional.

Professional activity is aimed at solving the following tasks: creation and acquisition of consumer value, satisfaction of individual needs of the labor subject, as well as development and improvement of a professional.

Professional activity is aimed at forming, developing and implementing the activities of an individual and a professional. It includes the solution of two tasks: professional development (development of professional abilities, motivation, etc.) and career development (growth and preservation of social and professional status).

Based on the analysis of the content and types of flexible skills, they can be included in the group of generally important professional qualities, and some of them in the category of meta professional (qualities related to self-development management). Because if we look at flexible skills from the point of view of tasks, they solve the general tasks of professional activity, and therefore are among the important operational qualities. In addition, the knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities acquired by a person in the process of development and training are important conditions that are

formed on the basis of competence. That is why, from this point of view, there are views that flexible skills can be a component of competence.

Now, if we focus on the types of grouping of flexible skills, we can see different views of research scientists:

1) V. Shipilov divides soft skills into the following groups:

- Basic communication skills - teamwork, negotiation, self-introduction, presentation, basic sales skills, public speaking, result orientation, business letter, client orientation.

- Self-management skills - emotion management, stress management, self-development management, planning and goal forecasting, time management, energy, enthusiasm, initiative, perseverance, reflection, use of feedback.

- Effective thinking skills - systematic thinking, creative thinking, structural thinking, logical thinking, searching and analyzing information, developing and making decisions, project thinking, tactical and strategic thinking.

- Management skills - performance management, planning, assigning tasks to employees, motivating, monitoring the implementation of tasks, mentoring (employee development) - mentoring, coaching, situational management and leadership, conducting consultations, giving feedback, project management, sending.

2): Tsybalyuk A. E., Vinogradova V. O. It includes the following contents:

Soft skills, focused on the person himself: managing his emotions, managing his development, self-education, self-regulation, etc. b.

- Soft skills aimed at other people:

- communication skills, teamwork and leadership skills, negotiation, empathy, etc. b.

- Soft skills, broad thinking skills aimed at solving general professional tasks (critical, strategic, systematic, etc.), problem solving, responsibility, decision-making, aptitude, performance, etc. b.

In addition, the authors propose the definition that soft skills are operationally important qualities that do not depend on the specifics of professional activity, but affect its effectiveness in solving general professional and meta professional tasks.

4) S.N. Scientists, led by Batsunov, classify into four groups:

- Basic communication skills or communication literacy (ability to listen, persuade and prove, negotiate, make presentations, speak in public, self-introduction, teamwork, result-oriented, business letter, etc.);

- Self-management skills that help to effectively control one's situation, time, processes (emotions, stress, self-development management, planning and goal forecasting, time management, energy, enthusiasm, initiative, perseverance, reflection, use of feedback);

- Effective thinking or intellectual thinking skills (systematic, creative, structured thinking, search and analysis of information, development and acceptance of decisions), responsible for managing the process in the mind, which help to systematically organize one's life and work;

- Management skills or foresight management (execution management, planning, setting tasks, motivation, monitoring the implementation of tasks, managing projects, changes), they are able to plan, motivate, implement their own changes, etc. b. responsible for management.

S.N. Based on research, Batsunov determines that traditional methods of training (lectures, seminars) are less effective in developing skills, and active and innovative methods of training (cases, simulations and projects) are more effective in developing "flexible" skills. Especially in language lessons, including foreign language lessons, adding dialogic forms of tasks; the use of exemplary video materials from the lives of professional and simply successful people; adding texts containing interesting information about career-related vocabulary, time management, personal growth; modeling of professional communication skills: speaking with a report, writing articles, etc. In particular, public speaking, which has never lost its relevance, is one of the most effective forms of presenting one's research results to the scientific community and showing readiness for cooperation. Language classes do not only develop speaking skills; Here, in addition to being able to show eloquence, body language, enthusiasm, and the ability to attract the attention of the audience, it is emphasized that it is possible to develop the skills of composing a speech text so that it is interesting and understandable not only for specialists, but also for all interested parties. In our opinion, the main advantage of this is the ability to work in two linguistic cultures, that is, the ability to develop a mindset and tolerance.

In our opinion, it is known that communication skills or communication skills form the main priority of social skills in any society. It has not lost its value even when it strives to develop in accordance with the world educational space and preserve its own image in accordance with cultural and historical values in order to form a national identity. In addition, the professional profile of many professions (especially the "person-to-person" group) is becoming one of the main criteria for the demand of young professionals in the labor market. In this regard, graduates with developed social skills, even with simple professional education, have a high chance of successful employment. Many employers emphasize that it is easy to improve professional competence by focusing on specific job duties of a young professional, and social skills can be a big obstacle if they are not sufficiently developed after graduating from the university. Here, the most important thing is to pay attention from a pragmatic point of view, that is, to understand that a young person who cannot communicate may not be an effective communicator in the future due to his personal characteristics.

In conclusion and based on the research work of scientists above, we can make the following conclusion:

1. Soft skills is not a synonym of skills, but a broader concept.

2. Soft skills are understood as a set of characteristics of personal qualities, intellectual features, socio-psychological skills, universal skills, non-professional and acquired skills.

3. Soft Skills have a great impact on the effectiveness of a person's professional, social, and personal life activities.

4. Not related to the specifics of professional activity, but is the same for different types of professional activities.

5. Formation and development of flexible skills of students is the main indicator of adaptation in the conditions of today's demands and rapidly changing society.

References:

1. Ermakov D. S., Aamantay Z.A., Learning and development of "flexible" skills as a psychological and pedagogical problem. materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference "Education and

Psychological and Pedagogical Science: Systemism, Succession, Innovation", devoted to the 110th anniversary of the birth of Academician T.T. Tazhibaeva - Almaty: Kazakh University, 2020. - P.17-19.

2. Tsybalyuk A.E., Vinogradova V.O. Psychological content of soft skills // Yaroslavsky pedagogic journal. - 2019 - No. 6 (111). - s. 120-127.

3. L.R. Gazizulina. Development of soft skills in the course of foreign-language preparation of graduate students. Vestnik of the University of Nizhny Novgorod. n.i. Lobachevsky. series: social sciences, 2019, No. 4 (56), S. 275–279

4. KS Yermeev. Directions for improving educational work with students in the context of digital transformation of society

PENALTIES AND INCENTIVES IN THE SCHOOL REGULATIONS OF THE BULGARIAN AND GREEK EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN VARNA OF THE 70s OF THE XIX CENTURY TO THE 20s OF THE XX CENTURY

Veselin Dimitrov Mihalev

Ph.D

Varna Free University „Chernorizetz Hrabar”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928275>

Abstract

The problem of the application of the system of penalties and incentives in the Bulgarian and Greek schools in Varna is not sufficiently researched in the scientific and pedagogical literature, because of that, in some school regulations are given only penalties to students, and the incentives are hardly affected. In the current post is made an attempt for the source of knowledge in pedagogical research of archival historical documents in the Bulgarian language and in the Greek language, proving the school's practice of educational institutions surveyed penalties and incentives of the students. The study aims to outline, on the one hand, the scope of the diversity and, on the other hand, the various forms of educational impact associated with their application during the researched period.

Keywords: encouragement, punishment, school, teacher, students, teaching, disciplinary regulations, discipline.

*„The best remedy of education is the hope of reward and the fear of penalty”
Sava Dobroplodni*

1. INTRODUCTION

The first written school regulations that regulate issues relating to penalties and incentives in the Bulgarian schools and in the Greek schools in Varna date back to the beginning of the 70s of the XX century. They are developed by teachers and members of school boards. Their introduction is the result of a conscious need of regulated rules and prohibitions in order to improve the school order. To achieve the aims of the pedagogical research, instruments were applied to which are generally accepted in the context of pedagogical methods in historiography – archiving method, facta – graphic method, history of our birthplace method and research of school documentation relating to the activity of the educational institutions in Varna during the period.

2. PENALTIES AND INCENTIVES IN BULGARIAN SCHOOLS

An important means of educational impact on students' behavior in the public – church Bulgarian school

in Varna in 70s of the XIX century are „**falagata**” and „**penalty plates**” with inscriptions: „*liar*”, „*thief*”, „*disturber*”, „*fool*” and „*careless*”. The use of „**falagata**” as an attribute of education appears to be primarily mean for impact. The punishment of public - church students by „**falagata**” bears the mark of medieval strictness. This simple and terrible thing often strikes genuine horror and it is used for tying the feet of the student who is beaten. For the fear of its applying the public - church students in Varna sincerely share: „*When we looked at it - „falagata”, it was creeping us out*” (Cerov, 1914: p. 9). The student who is punished by his mutual teacher depending on the severity of the misconduct must stand with hanging „**penalty plate**” on his neck for a certain time, facing students and in many cases he is escorted by his classmates around the streets of the city. According to I. Cerov, this punishment has a strong impact on personality education of adolescents.

In his pedagogical activity the teacher Sava Dobroplodni harshly condemns the fight as a penal mean and he is convinced that: „*the best remedy of education is the hope of reward and the fear of penalty*”. For the